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**EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF ADOLESCENTS IN RELATION TO
THEIR FAMILY CLIMATE*****Research paper in Education*****Dr. Gagandeep Kaur,**

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Abstract

Emotional development in children and adolescents stems from their interactions at home with parents and siblings. Parent-child interaction and parent's way to deal with their children/develop certain attitude among children, which govern their relationships and interactions at home and outside. The present study was undertaken to study the emotional intelligence of adolescents in relation to their family climate. The sample consisted of 200 students of IX class both male and female adolescents from private as well as government schools of Amritsar district only. The findings of the study revealed: i) There exists no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of boys and girls adolescents. ii) There exists no significant difference between the family climate of boys and girls adolescents. iii) There exists positive and significant correlation between the family climate and emotional intelligence of adolescents.

The rhythm and pace of modern life gives us little time to assimilate, reflect and react. Our bodies are geared to slower rhythm. We need time to be introspective, but we don't get it. Emotions have their own agenda and time table, but our rushed lives give them no space, no air

time and so they go underground. In addition to intelligence, emotions are equally responsible for performance. In fact, emotional intelligence is an indispensable activator and enhancer of IQ. According to Goleman (1955), IQ accounts for only 20% of persons success in life, the remaining 80% largely depends on a person's emotional intelligence. It is the most important determinant of professional and personal success in life. Accordingly to Goleman (1966), emotional intelligence refers to the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of other, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in ourselves and in our relationships".

According to Stein and Book (2000), Emotional Intelligence has to do with "ability to read the political and social environment and landscape them to intuitively grasp what others want and need, their strengths and weaknesses are to remain unruffled by stress, and to engage the kind of person that others want to be around".

Goleman (1995) defines it is a cluster of traits or abilities relating to the emotional side of life Goleman suggest that El consists of five major parts:

- Knowing our own emotions
- Managing our own emotions
- Motivating ourselves
- Recognizing and influencing other's emotions
- Handling relationships.

Emotional intelligence is 'the capability to understand the emotions, to produce and enhance emotions in an aim to support thinking, to understand the emotional data and to regulate the emotions as a reflector in order to ensure emotional and intellectual development' (Mayer & Salovey, 1997). Emotional development in children and adolescents stems from their interactions at home with parents and siblings. Parent-child interaction and parent's way to deal with their children/develop certain attitude among children, which govern their relationships and interactions at home and outside.

Family is the environment where the children learn to use their faculties and understand and cope with the physical world. It is the place, where they learn how family

relationships work, by observing their parents, grandparents, siblings and rest of the family members deal with each other.

Family environment where the foundations of emotional intelligence are first laid is a setting the child grows up and acquires some information relating to life. Family environment bearing healthy and high quality characteristics affects the development of the child in many ways like ego concept of the child and his/her emotional and social development. Social status of the parents, the residence, relations within the family, the number of siblings and the relations among the siblings determine the characteristics of the family environment. Wiltfang and Scarbecz (1990) have defined the family environment so that the definition will cover the characteristics determining the social status of the parents like educational level, occupational status and professions of the parents as well as the quality of the residence, working conditions of the parents and relations of the siblings. Grolnick and Slowiaczek (1994) define the environment in which the family lives as a setting of learning which has vital effects on the child. The child is affected by the sources of the family environment to a great degree while gaining experiences relating to life. The perception of the individual of one's family climate seems to affect the understanding of emotions and skills required to manage the emotions so as to solve various psycho-social and emotional problems. Lewin (1955) reported that parents with unsatisfactory family climate were found to be causative in children's psychological disorders. Nagaraja (1977) concluded that the parent-child relationship is paramount predictor of emotional development in the children.

Kaur and Jaswal (2005) revealed that family climate is significantly and positively related to high performance level of emotional intelligence and number of respondents scoring "Unfavourable Family Climate" was far less for various dimensions for high performance of emotional intelligence.

Ravindranandan and Raju (2008) revealed that there will be significant differences in emotional Intelligence and quality of life among the parents on the basis of income and also significant gender differences among the samples on emotional intelligence and quality of life.

Parents influence the children by what they think, how they feel and what they do in the family. Family is the child's world in which the personality is shaped and his character is formed.

Healthy relations in the family are a medium for providing wholesome and adjusted personalities respondents for success. It is emphasized in the studies that the family environment is highly important in the emotional and social development of the child. Emotional processes are affected by the family environment much.

The problems adolescents face today are more strenuous and complicated than they used to be in the past. With so much of exposure, both positive and negative, adolescents face situations of indecisiveness and malaise where they are not getting the key emotional and social skills and competencies they need for leading a proper life. With the breakdown of the joint family system into nuclear families, both father and mother are working, high expectations on achievements, over ambitious attitudes and cut throat competitions, the adolescent is bound to face anxiety, frustration, anger, jealousy and many such emotions which, if not tackled and channelized properly, can manifest as malpractice and hopelessness in the form of a poor emotional state.

The present study has been undertaken with an objective to study the emotional intelligence among adolescents in relation to their family climate.

HYPOTHESES

Ho.1 There exists no significant difference between emotional intelligence of boys and girls.

Ho.2: There exists no significant difference between family climate of boys and girls adolescents.

Ho.3: There exists no significant relationship between family climate and emotional intelligence of adolescents.

METHOD

Type of Research

Descriptive method was used to undertake the present study.

Sample

The sample consisted of 200 students of IX class both male and female adolescents from private as well as government schools of Amritsar district only.

Tools Used

- (i) Emotional Intelligence Scale (Hyde, Dethle & Dhar, 1971).
- (ii) Family Environment Scale by (Bhatia & Chadha, 1993).

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

In order to test the hypotheses formulated, following statistical techniques were employed for the analysis of the data:

- 't' test was applied to determine the significance of difference between mean scores of male and female adolescents for emotional intelligence and family climate.
- Correlation was calculated to see the relationship between the two variables.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

HYPOTHESIS 1

“There exists no significant difference between emotional intelligence of boys and girls.”

To verify Hypothesis 1, raw scores were obtained from girls and boys on emotional intelligence scale. The mean scores and S.D were calculated and entered in Table 1. Further ‘t’ value was calculated to test the significance of difference between mean scores of emotional intelligence of girls and boys.

Table 1: Showing Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-value of emotional intelligence of Girls and Boys

Group	Mean	SD	SED	't'	Inference
Girls	132.30	11.59	1.52	0.368	Insignificant at 0.01 level
Boys	131.74	9.76			

Table 1 reveals that mean scores of emotional intelligence of girls and boys were 132.30 and 131.74 respectively. The obtained ‘t’ value 0.368 was found insignificant even at 0.05 level, which reflected that gender differences does not exist with respect to emotional intelligence. Hence the null Hypothesis 1 stating that there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of boys and girls is not rejected.

HYPOTHESIS 2

"There exists no significant difference between family climate of boys and girls adolescents"

To verify Hypothesis 2 raw scores were obtained from girls and boys on family climate scale. The mean scores and S.D were calculated and entered in Table 2. Further 't' value was calculated to test the significance of difference between mean scores of family climate of boys and girls adolescents.

Table 2: Mean, Standard Deviation, and 't' value of family climate of boys and girls

Group	Mean	SD	SED	't'	Inference
Boys	238.53	12.81	1.89	1.37	Insignificant at 0.05 level
Girls	341.13	14.00			

Table 2 revealed that mean family climate scores of boys and girls were 238.53 and 341.13 respectively. The obtained 't' value 1.37 was found insignificant even at 0.05 level, which reflected that gender difference does not exist with respect to family climate. Hence the null Hypothesis 2 stating that "There is no significant differences between family climate of boys and girls adolescents" is not rejected

HYPOTHESIS 3

'There exists no significant relationship between family climate and emotional intelligence of adolescents.'

In order to verify Hypothesis 3, 'r' for raw data was calculated and entered in Table 3.

Table 3 :Showing the Mean, Standard Deviation, and 'r' value of family climate and emotional intelligence

VARIABLES	N	r	Inference
Study Habits	200	+0.74	significant at 0.01 level
Home environment			

Table 3 reveals that the family climate and emotional intelligence were positively correlated ($r = 0.74$) which indicated that higher correlation exists between family climate and emotional intelligence. The positive correlation reveals that adolescents who get supportive, cohesive and adjustable family environment have higher level of emotional intelligence

Hence the null Hypothesis 3, stating that, “There is no significant relationship between family climate and emotional intelligence” stands rejected.

Main Findings

- There exists no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of boys and girls adolescents.
- There exists no significant difference between the family climate of boys and girls adolescents.
- There exists positive and significant correlation between the family climate and emotional intelligence of adolescents.

Educational Implications

- Parents should give friendly environment to their children so that they can express their feelings and emotions openly as the basic components of emotional relationships are laid down and shaped by the security or insecurity of parent-child relationships.
- Parents should avoid aggression and conflict among themselves in front of their child.
- Parents should introspect their respective roles in making these relationships healthy as for most children; there is a cascading effect in which early family relationships provide necessary support for effectively engaging in peer world.
- Parents of adolescents having low emotional intelligence should provide emotional security to their children rather than rebuking them.
- Parents’ teacher meeting should be brought about frequently at school, where parents should be educated or provided information regarding the effect of family climate on the emotional intelligence of the children.

- Counselling sessions should be held with students facing problems at home.

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